

ULTRASONIC MEASUREMENT OF THE ANISOTROPIC DAMAGE TENSOR

IN A CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITE

Bertrand AUDIOIN and Stéphane BASTE

Laboratoire de Mécanique Physique,

U.R.A. C.N.R.S. n° 867, Université de Bordeaux I.

351, Cours de la Liberation, 33405-TALENCE Cedex, France.

ABSTRACT

During a loading process a 2D ceramic-ceramic (SiC-SiC) composite, which exhibits a non-linear anisotropic mechanical behaviour, is characterized by means of an ultrasonic device.

Firstly, the main principles of the ultrasonic characterization are given. The numerical processing of the wave velocities data, which enables the identification of all the stiffness coefficients of an orthorhombic material, is briefly described. The reliability and accuracy of the identification are also discussed. Secondly, an analysis of the nature of the anisotropic damage variable and its introduction in the constitutive laws is realized by means of simple considerations. Finally, the ultrasonic characterization of the SiC-SiC 2D stiffness tensor at twenty three levels of stress is performed during a tensile test up to failure. This leads to the identification of the proposed model and to the analysis of the micromechanical phenomena that occur during the test.

KEYWORDS: Ultrasonic; Characterization; Anisotropy; damage; ceramic/matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites show a typical non-linear behaviour due to matrix microcracking. Because of the initial texture of the composite and of the anisotropy induced by the microcracks growth, their behaviour is strongly anisotropic. Consequently, we have developed an innovative ultrasonic interferometer [1] with which we realize the complete characterization of the stiffness tensor of those orthorhombic materials under load.

2. ULTRASONIC CHARACTERIZATION

In anisotropic solids exhibiting a purely elastic behaviour, the stress-strain relationship:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl}, \quad (1)$$

can be written [2] in term of the small displacement field of an elastic plane wave. It leads to the wave equation, which we write in its Christoffel form:

$$\left(\Gamma_{ij} - \rho v^2 \delta_{ij} \right) P_j = 0, \quad \text{with } \Gamma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} n_k n_l, \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density, \vec{P} the polarization vector, \vec{n} the direction of propagation, v the velocity and δ_{ij} Kronecker's symbol. Since the operator Γ_{ij} is symmetrical, its eigenvalues ρv^2 are real and the eigenvectors \vec{P} are mutually orthogonal. So, three modes can propagate along the direction \vec{n} with different velocities and polarizations. One polarization is longitudinal (or quasi-longitudinal Q.L.) and the two others are transverse (or quasi-transverse Q.T.), with respect to \vec{n} . The velocities are solutions of the following third degree equation of the unknown ρv^2 :

$$\det \left(\Gamma_{ij} - \rho v^2 \delta_{ij} \right) = 0. \quad (3)$$

The ultrasonic characterization purpose is to solve the inverse problem of recovering the elastic coefficients C_{ijkl} from the wave speed measurements. Each experimental value of the roots ρv^2 gives a non-linear equation (3) of the stiffness tensor coefficients. The acquisition of the wave speed of the generated modes for various propagation directions leads to a set of such equations. Its resolution is a numerical analysis problem which we solve by an optimization process described in section 2.2.

2.1 Acquisition of ultrasonic wave velocities. As detailed in [1], wave speed measurements are performed by using ultrasonic pulses which are refracted through a plate sample immersed in water. Varying the incidence angle provides numerous directions and modes in the sample. One, two or three modes will reach the receiver with a time delay related to their respective velocities.

The time delay between the received pulses and the reference signal acquired without the sample can be computed by classical input-output intercorrelation. Some metrological problems may appear when quasi longitudinal and quasi transverse modes have not sufficiently different velocities (mode-mixing) or when the propagation occurs in lossy media (effect of the porosity). We have shown that the measurement can then be improved using a signal processing based on the use of the Hilbert transform [3].

2.2 Recovering of the stiffness tensor. Let us consider the set of equations (3) which, for the most general case, links the twenty one stiffness coefficients of a triclinic symmetry to the ultrasonic wave propagation velocities. Assuming an orthorhombic symmetry, the number of unknowns decreases to nine. Likewise, when the direction of propagation is included in a principal plane of such a symmetry, four of those coefficients interfere in the propagation equations. Since one of them (C_{11} in the axes of FIG. 1) is directly calculated from the normal incidence velocity measurement, three constants must still be identified. In such a plane,

equations (3) can be factorized and become bi-squared equations of v . Because of the continuity law, the third mode is not generated.

Let $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$ be the rank of an experimental value v_k of the velocity in the direction \vec{n}_k . Because of the experimental shift, the measured values $\lambda_k = \rho v_k^2$ are then approximately equal to the roots of the equations:

$$f(C_{ij}, V_k) = \lambda_k^2 - \lambda_k(\Gamma_{11} + \Gamma_{22}) + \Gamma_{11}\Gamma_{22} - \Gamma_{12}^2 \quad (4)$$

The optimum values of the stiffness coefficients [4], in the least square sense, are those for which the non-linear function (4) reaches its minimum value for the whole set of N experimental data. In figure 1 are reported the optimum slowness curves which are defined as the inverses of wave speeds versus direction. They are obtained by minimizing the functional:

$$F(C_{ij}) = \sum_{\lambda_k} f(C_{ij}, \lambda_k)^2 \quad (5)$$

using a Newton Raphson iterative procedure. The convexity can be ensured with the improvements described in [5].

FIGURE 1: Slowness curves in a principal plane of symmetry in a SiC-SiC 2D composite; crosses: experimental data - solid lines: optimum fit.

The measurements made in the two accessible principal planes enable the identification of seven coefficients of the stiffness tensor, namely: $C_{11}, C_{22}, C_{12}, C_{66}$ for a propagation in the 1,2 plane, and $C_{11}, C_{33}, C_{13}, C_{55}$ in the 1,3 plane.

When dealing with a non principal plane, the three modes can propagate and the third degree equations (3) cannot be factorized. But the number of unknowns is now reduced to the two remaining coefficients C_{23} and C_{44} . A functional built the same way as (5) is minimized [6]; for that purpose, the data required are the wave speeds measured in a non principal plane, and the elastic coefficients identified by propagation in the two principal planes. Its non strict convexity leads to some problems discussed in section 2.3.

or Q.T.2. In those conditions the functional is very "flat" and the confidence interval which, by the linearization included in measures the gap's depth, is very extended.

FIGURE 2: Slowness curves in a non principal plane of a SiC-SiC 2D composite

3. THE ANISOTROPIC DAMAGE INTERNAL VARIABLE

The purpose of the continuum damage concept [8] is to describe the internal structure change that occurs in certain materials under stress. Damage is defined as the progressive deterioration of materials due to nucleation and growth of microcracks.

Those internal changes affect the physical and mechanical properties of materials. Degradation of one of those property is an indirect measurement of damage. The microscopic deterioration having, in general, an unmistakable anisotropic character, the measure of damage depends on its direction of evaluation \vec{n} [9]. It is necessary to look for the correct tensorial writing of the damage variable.

3.1 Tensorial nature. As a result of the arbitrary nature of the internal variables choice, which is inherent to the phenomenological theories, the literature abounds in different and often contradictory models [10]. It is clear that the damage variable must be tensorial to be invariant under a change of basis. The order of this tensor must be examined (0: scalar, 1: vector, 2, 4, ...).

It appears that the proposed representations: scalar variable [11,12], vector [13,14,15], second-order tensor [16,17,18,19,20,21], are based on a *a priori* assumption made on the microstructure according to the simplification level of the model. The choice of a fourth order tensorial damage variable, associated with its correct introduction in the constitutive laws, is the general formulation which leads to the description of any stiffness tensor change due to damage.

3.2 Introduction in the constitutive law. A common way of introducing the damage variable in the constitutive law is offered by the effective stress concept [11]. The reduction of the cross

section area involved by microcracking increases the stress. The effective stress σ_{eff} is defined as:

$$\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\sigma}{1-d} \quad (8)$$

A sane material, whose stiffness is C and which is submitted to σ_{eff} is considered equivalent to the damaged material. In order to assure the symmetry of the elasticity tensor, an energy equivalence must be postulated [18]. For practical use, the damage tensor must be diagonal, and the damaged stiffnesses are:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ii} &= (1-D_{ii})^2 C_{ii}^0 \quad ; \\ C_{ij} &= (1-D_{ii})(1-D_{jj}) C_{ij}^0 \quad , \quad i \neq j \quad . \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Thus this model introduces a coupling between the off-diagonal stiffnesses and the diagonal ones. Since ultrasonic measurement allows the independent identification of D_{ii} , D_{jj} and of C_{ij} 's variation, it has been shown that the coupling involved is not experimentally verified [22]. Finally, the definition of damage as the reduction of the cross-sectional area, involved on the effective stress concept, is difficult to generalize to the tridimensional case. This extension leads to follow the stiffness tensor change through the stress tensor variation. Those two variables having different tensorial nature (second-order for σ and fourth-order for C), it involves coupling of directions without any physical foundations [23].

It becomes obvious that the Young modulus variation is the only correct measure of damage which is experimentally realizable. The tridimensional generalization leads naturally to define damage as a change of the elasticity tensor. This definition is analogous to the one proposed by Ortiz [24] in which the values of the elastic constants themselves are taken as a characterization of the state of damage of the material. The following approach allows to introduce explicitly the damage variable. The elasticity tensor can be written in an additive form [23]:

$$C = C_0 - C_c \quad , \quad (10)$$

in terms of the stiffness tensor C_0 of the uncracked material and of the loss of stiffness C_c due to the microcracks. The variation of the stiffness tensor :

$$\omega = C_c = C_0 - C \quad , \quad (11)$$

is selected as an internal variable representing the current state of the microcracking of the material. Like the initial elasticity tensor C_0 , the effective stiffness is a fourth rank symmetrical tensor, and so does the damage variable ω . With the introduction of usual abbreviated subscripts notation, equation (11) becomes :

$$\omega_{ij} = C_{ij}^0 - C_{ij} \quad , \quad i, j = 1 \text{ to } 6 \quad . \quad (12)$$

The components of this tensor have a clearly identifiable physical meaning, form a finite set of data and a fully anisotropic behaviour can be described. The limit of the model is again experimental: its identification (see section 2) requires the assumption that the material stays orthorhombic during the sollicitation.

Traditionally, in phenomenological models based on the thermodynamics of internal variables, the damage parameter varies from zero for the initial state to the critical value $d=1$ at the failure

of the volume element [11]. To this end it is necessary to "normalize" the components of the damage tensor to their thermodynamically admissible maximum values ω_{ij}^{lim} such that the elasticity tensor still is a positive defined operator [23]. We have:

$$D_{ii} = \frac{\omega_{ii}}{\omega_{ii}^{lim}} = 1 - \frac{C_{ii}}{C_{ii}^0} \quad , \quad i = 1 \text{ to } 6, \quad (13)$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{\omega_{ij}}{\omega_{ij}^{lim}} = \frac{C_{ij}^0 - C_{ij}}{C_{ij}^0 + \text{Sign}(C_{ij}^0 - C_{ij}) \sqrt{C_{ii}^0 (1 - D_{ii}) C_{jj}^0 (1 - D_{jj})}} \quad , \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 6, \quad i \neq j \quad . \quad (14)$$

With

$$\begin{aligned} D_{ij} &= D_{ij}^+ \quad \text{if } \text{Sign}(\omega_{ij}) > 0 \quad , \\ D_{ij} &= D_{ij}^- \quad \text{if } \text{Sign}(\omega_{ij}) < 0 \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

we find the constitutive equations of the damaged material :

$$C_{ii} = C_{ii}^0 (1 - D_{ii}) \quad , \quad i = 1 \text{ to } 6, \quad (16)$$

$$C_{ij} = C_{ij}^0 (1 - D_{ij}) \mp D_{ij}^\pm \sqrt{C_{ii}^0 (1 - D_{ii}) C_{jj}^0 (1 - D_{jj})} \quad , \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 6, \quad i \neq j \quad . \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) expresses the effect of both D_{ii} and D_{jj} damages in the directions i and j upon the coupling coefficient C_{ij} . The existence of D_{ii} and D_{jj} parameters in the C_{ij} damage-growth law, is solely due to thermodynamic restrictions on the sign of the M_{ij} minor introduced for normalization.

4. STIFFNESS CHANGES AND DAMAGE EVOLUTION CAUSED BY MATRIX CRACK

The material is the 2D SiC-SiC sample yet characterized in section 2. The composite is fabricated by Société Européenne de Propulsion from preforms built up from multiple layers of SiC cloths. The SiC matrix was added by a chemical vapor infiltration (C.V.I.) process which results in samples with varying porosity [25]. The axes that are considered in the following are those of figure 1. The main length of the sample, in direction 3, is 190 mm and its thickness is 3.5 mm. The material presents under load a particular behaviour with a typical non-linearity due to the strain-to-failure of the matrix which is smaller than the fiber one.

For this experiments, a special interferometer has been built which allows the propagation of ultrasonic waves in any direction around the sample and consequently its complete characterization. This immersed interferometer has been located in a classical tensile machine.

The ultrasonic characterization requires that the test be realised by steps. All during the angular investigation of the three planes, the stress is controled to be constant. This tensile test has been realised in two times. A first load up to 180 MPa with seventeen steps for characterization; and a second test up to failure preceded by a return to a zero load.

The results of the stiffness tensor identifications and their relative confidence interval are plotted in figure 3 and the damage parameters calculated by (13) and (14) are shown in figure 4.

4.1 Transverse hardening by Poison effect. From 0 to 20 MPa a transverse hardening appears which is mainly sensible on C_{22} but also on C_{12} and C_{66} . The variation of C_{22} is about 150 MPa and the parameter D_{22} is negative ($D_{22} = -0.4$). This hardening is due to the closure of pre-existing cracks and porosities whose volume along the transverse directions is small. Such a transverse hardening has yet been observed on numerical simulations based on micro-mechanic concepts [24,26]. Its measurement is reported here for the first time.

FIGURE 3: Stiffness tensor coefficients and their 90 % relative confidence interval

4.2 Damage threshold. Up to a 90 MPa stress, the stiffness tensor doesn't vary anymore in a sensible manner. Afterwards, the matrix microcracking begins and the moduli decrease. The cracks grow preferentially in the plane transverse to the loading direction since D_{33} exhibits an increase of 0.5. But, because of the composite texture, it also propagate along the fibers: C_{11} and C_{22} also decrease heavily. It is worth noting that this microcracking also has an important effect on shear moduli, and particularly on those relative to the planes that contain the loading direction i.e. C_{44} and C_{55} . The damage level reached by the damage parameters relative to those shear moduli are similar to the one reached by C_{33} .

FIGURE 4: Evolution of damage tensor coefficients

4.3 Matrix cracking saturation. When a 130 MPa stress has been reached, the evolution of the stiffness coefficients becomes much slower. The stress to failure of the matrix has been

exceeded and its microcracking has reached its saturation level. Note that during the second tensile test, if we do not consider the cracks opening and closure effects, the values of the stiffness coefficients are similar to those attained during the first load at 180 MPa. Beyond 130 MPa, the damage increases slowly and the elasticity of the material is close to that of the fibers. Their failure occurs quite suddenly around 230 MPa.

5. CONCLUSION

The behaviour of matrix ceramic composites is strongly influenced by the dominant role of microcracking. Those internal mechanisms of degradation have a perceptible effect upon elastic properties of those materials.

If the classical mechanic metrology allows the measurement of a weak number of stiffness and damage parameters, ultrasonic techniques leads to the complete identification of the elasticity tensor of an orthorhombic material. An immersed interferometer located in a tensile machine gives access to the variation of the nine elastic stiffnesses. Nine associated components of the anisotropic damage tensor were introduced to fully describe the 2D SiC-SiC tridimensional non-linear behaviour under tensile test.

Acknowledgement:

This work was partially supported by Société Européenne de Propulsion under contract n°451957.

REFERENCES:

1. J. Roux, et. al., *Rev. Phys. Appl.*, **20**, 351-358 (1985).
2. B.A. Auld, *Acoustic Fields and Waves in Solids*, vol.1, Wiley Interscience, NY, 1973.
3. B. Audoin and J. Roux, *Rev. Phys. Appl.*, **25**, 1011-1017 (1990).
4. B. Hosten and B. Castagnède, *C.R. Acad. Sci. Paris*, 296 II, 297-300 (1983).
5. S. Baste and M. Deschamps, *C.R. Acad. Sci. Paris*, **309 II**, 1521-1526 (1989).
6. S. Baste and B. Hosten, *Rev. Phys. App.*, **25**, 161-168 (1990).
7. B. Audoin, S. Baste and B. Castagnède, *C.R. Acad. Sci. Paris*, to be published (1991).
8. L.M. Kachanov, *Izv. AN SSSR, Otd. Tekn. Nauk*, **8**, 26-31 (1958).
9. P. Ladeveze, *Proceedings of JNC6*, Pluralis, Paris, 1986, pp. 685-697.
10. D. Krajcinovic, *Mecha. Mater.*, **8**, 117-197 (1989).
11. J. Lemaitre and J.L. Chaboche, *J. Meca. Appl.*, **2**, 167-189 (1978).
12. B. Budiansky, R.J. O'Connell, *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, **12**, 81-97 (1976).
13. L. Davison and A.L. Stevens, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **44**, 668-674 (1973).
14. D. Krajcinovic and G.U. Fondelka, *J. Appl. Mech.*, **48**, 809-815 (1981).
15. R. Talreja, *Proc. R. Soc. Lond.*, **A399**, 195-216 (1985).
16. L.M. Kachanov, *J. Eng. Mech. Div.*, *ASCE* **106**, 1039-1051 (1980).
17. S. Murakami and N. Ohno in A.R.S. Ponter and D.R. Hayhurst, ed., *Creep in Structures*, Springer, Berlin, 1981, pp. 922-944.
18. J.P. Cordebois and F. Sidoroff, *J. Méca. Th.Appl.*, special issue, 45-60 (1982).
19. A. Litewka, *Arch. Mech.*, **37**, 631-642 (1985).
20. S. Murakami and T. Imaizumi, *J. Méca. Théor. Appl.*, **1**, 743-761 (1982).
21. J.L. Chaboche in J. P. Boehler, ed., *Proceedings of EuroMECH 115*, Villard de lens, France, Coll. Int. du C.N.R.S., 1979, pp. 738-760.
22. S. Baste, R. El Guerjouma and A. Gerard, *Rev. Phys. Appl.*, **24**, 721-731 (1989).
23. S. Baste and B. Audoin, *European Journal of Mechanics*, to be published (1991).
24. M. Ortiz, *Mecha. Mater.*, **4**, 67-93 (1985).
25. E. Inghels and J. Lamon, *Revue Phys. Appl.*, **23**, 193-200 (1988).
26. S. Andrieux and al., *J. Meca. Théor. Appl.*, **5**, 471-513 (1986).